

MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION FOR PARTICLE-FILLED RTM IN 3D FIBROUS PREFORMS

L. Marchand^{1,2}, S. Comas-Cardona¹, C. Binetruy¹ and A. Hautefeuille²

¹Nantes Université, Ecole Centrale Nantes, CNRS, GeM, UMR 6183, F-44000 Nantes, France
1 rue de la Noë, Nantes, 44321, France

Email: leonie.marchand@ec-nantes.fr, sebastien.comas@ec-nantes.fr and christophe.binetruy@ec-nantes.fr, web page: <https://gem.ec-nantes.fr/>

²ArianeGroup SAS

Les Cinq Chemins, 5 Rue de Touban, 33185, Le Haillan, France

Email: alexandre.hautefeuille@ariane.group, web page: <https://ariane.group/>

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ABSTRACT

In the case of severe thermo-mechanical loads, the composite materials of this study are manufactured through Resin Transfer Molding process in which a particle-filled thermosetting resin is injected into a 3D fibrous preform.

The challenge is to control the process by building a model that couples flow in porous media, particle filtration, and material properties' evolution induced by the filtration phenomenon. Such a model requires material properties related to particle-filled resin rheology and fibrous preform permeability as inputs.

Experimental methods were used in order to characterize the materials of the study taking into account the fibrous preform architecture. An initial phase consisted in characterizing the particle-filled fluid with experimental tests and determining the preform microstructure with micro-tomography. In a second phase, a new non-destructive method was developed to measure the three-dimensional permeability of a 3D anisotropic fibrous reinforcement using an air-flow bench.

The material data generated from the characterization will further be implemented in the coupled flow-filtration model.

1 INTRODUCTION

3D fiber-reinforced composite materials are often used for thermal protection systems (TPS) that are exposed to severe thermo-mechanical loads. The 3D composites investigated in this study are manufactured through RTM (Resin Transfer Molding) process in which a thermosetting resin is injected into a 3D fibrous preform (Fig. 1). The 3D composites are further functionalized by two means: (i)

Figure 1: Study process overview.

adding fillers to the resin and (ii) generating a fillers' content gradient in the fibrous preform. Therefore, the challenge consists in controlling this process, which involves the flow of particle-filled resin through a three-dimensional fibrous preform.

In order to control the particle content during the injection, one must build a model that couples flow in porous media, particle filtration, and material properties' (e.g., viscosity and permeability) evolution induced by the filtration phenomenon [1], [2], [3], [4]. Such a model requires material properties related to particle-filled resin rheology and fibrous preform permeability as inputs. Literature showed that the resin viscosity increases with the particle concentration. Because of the addition of particles, the particle-filled fluid may exhibit different behaviours than the neat fluid [1], [4]. Previous studies developed different experimental methods for fibrous reinforcement permeability measurement. These methods are usually destructive and apply to 2D reinforcements [5].

This work aims to extend the understanding of the flow behaviour and architecture of the three-dimensional fibrous network geometries during Resin Transfer Moulding. Experimental methods were used in order to characterize the materials of the study taking into account the fibrous preform architecture.

An initial phase of the work consisted in characterizing the particle-filled fluid and determining the preform microstructure. The rheology of the particle-filled fluid was analysed in order to determine the influence of filler content on the viscosity. Then, micro-computed tomography was used to analyse the three-dimensional fibrous preform architecture. In a second phase, a new non-destructive method was developed to measure the three-dimensional permeability of the fibrous reinforcement using an air-flow bench. Using an inverse method, the preform permeability 3D tensor is determined from experimental and numerical simulation results

2 MATERIALS

A first phase of the work consisted in characterizing the materials of the study. The particle-filled fluid rheology was determined and the 3D fibrous preform microstructure was analyzed.

2.1 Suspension characterization

A model suspension was chosen in order to develop experimental methods by fluid flow. Glycerin SOLVAGREEN® from Carl Roth was mixed with ethanol at a percentage of 65/35% by mass. The glycerin-ethanol is then mixed with carbon blacks using the T25 digital Ultra-Turrax disperser to homogenize the suspension. The model suspension of the study is studied with variable particle contents to measure the viscosity as a function of particle concentration as shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Evolution of the suspension viscosity as a function of the particle content.

2.1 Fibrous preform morphology

The 3D fibrous preform architecture is obtained by non-woven horizontal ply stacking made of carbon fibers whose orientations vary periodically in a balanced way. The three-dimensional structure is built by transferring fibers in the vertical direction, i.e. through the thickness. Samples of the dry fibrous preform were analyzed by micro-tomography to better examine its microstructure. The micro-tomography tests were conducted with a XRadia XCT-400 to obtain images of the fibrous preform slices through its thickness. According to the sample size, the image resolution varies from $\sim 40\mu\text{m}$ to $\sim 6\mu\text{m}$. The 3D volume were reconstructed from the micro-tomography images (Fig. 3 left) and the fiber orientations was analyzed by image treatment. As shown in figure 3 (right), in-plane images were segmented by fiber orientation using the ImageJ plugin OrientationJ.

Figure 3: 3D reconstruction of the fibrous preform (left) and image segmentation by fiber orientation (right) of micro-tomography images. The color map indicates the orientations of the fibers.

3 A NEW NON-DESTRUCTIVE 3D PERMEABILITY METHOD FOR ANISOTROPIC 3D FIBROUS PREFORM

Accurate measurement of the three-dimensional permeability tensor of fibrous preforms is essential for the prediction and optimization of resin flow in Liquid Composite Molding processes. In 3D fibrous reinforcements, resin can flow not only in the in-plane directions but also through the thickness, due to the presence of fibers transferred in the transverse direction. Moreover, because the fibrous preform presents an anisotropic three-dimensional architecture, the determination of the 3D permeability tensor becomes more complex.

To this day, different experimental methods of fibrous reinforcement permeability measurement exist [5]. While experimental methods to measure 1D, 2D or 3D permeability of fibrous reinforcements are commonly used, they are often limited to destructive methods since liquid is used to saturate the fiber bed. Non-destructive methods such as gas-based permeability measurement offer a cleaner, relatively faster alternative. By imposing gases like air to flow through dry preforms, pressure or flow rate difference is measured to determine permeability values [6], [7]. However, these experimental methods are typically constrained to 1D and 2D flows.

We thus propose a new experimental method to determine the 3D permeability tensor of a thick anisotropic fibrous preform using a transient air flow using an inverse method. This method has the advantage to be non-destructive, to limit the number of sample to the to-be-processed preform and of not requiring the sealing of the material.

3.1 Description of the experimental setup

The test rig (Fig. 4) consists in a cavity, where the fibrous preform is placed, formed by a bottom plate, a frame and a top plate. The cavity is sealed with the two plates above and below the preform (in

contact), leaving the side faces free. Depending on the preform thickness, the frame can be adapted. The bottom plate presents several locations in order to place pressure sensors according to the measurement configuration and the preform geometry. Moreover, the top plate presents one pressure sensor location. On the bottom plate, an air inlet is connected to a vacuum pump allowing imposing pressure in the cavity for the measurement. During a measurement, a transient air flow is thus imposed inside the cavity where the fibrous preform is, from an initial pressure P_0 to P_{end} . An automated data acquisition line saves the pressure sensor measurement. It is possible to conduct the experiments by raising pressure method (RPM) or dropping pressure method (DPM). These tests were conducted using the RPM method where the pressure of the cavity during the measurement goes from $P_0 = P_{vacuum}$ to $P_{end} = P_{atm}$ by opening the inlet to ambient air.

Figure 4: Schematic diagram of the experimental setup.

The aim of the experiment is to measure the pressure difference at several locations of the fibrous preform during the imposed transient air flow. This pressure difference between sensors allows determining each component of the 3D permeability tensor. This experimental method is decoupled in two steps (Fig. 5): (step 1) in-plane flow and (step 2) transverse flow.

Figure 5: Schematic diagrams of the in-plane (step 1, sensor P5 is not active) and transverse (step 2) measurement configurations.

During step 1, air flows in through the inlet point and the pressure in the cavity (out of the preform) is measured by the sensor P4. This measurement represents the pressure imposed on the lateral sides of the fibrous preform because the pressure in the cavity is considered to be homogenised quasi instantaneously. Then, air flows through the fibrous preform and the pressure is measured at points P1, P2 and P3.

During step 2, a transverse airflow is imposed by letting the air in at the centre of the preform, on the bottom plate side. The pressure measurement by sensor P5 is added, which is located on the upper plate, on the top face of the preform and above the inlet. In this way, air flows within the entire preform and the pressure sensors P1, P2 and P3 measure the in-plane pressure as in step 1. In addition, the sensor P4, placed in the cavity, measures the pressure outside the preform to be implemented as a boundary condition applied at the lateral sides of the preform.

Figure 6 shows the experimental pressure measured by the sensors in both configurations (step 1 and step 2). The transient phase of the pressure curves is observed and can be distinguished between sensors. This transient part of the curves highlights the delay between sensors, which will be used for numerical resolution and the permeability identification.

During these measurements, only one material sample is tested and the fibrous preform remains intact after each test. Thus, the tests can be repeated as many times as necessary.

Figure 6: Experimental results of pressure sensors in both configurations: step 1 in-plane (left) and step 2 transverse (right)

3.2 Numerical model

Because of non-linearity and the three-dimensional flow, numerical model is needed to extract the permeability tensor components. The simulation tool COMSOL Multiphysics® is used to implement air flow through the 3D fibrous preform. Two distinct numerical models are established replicating both experimental measurement steps.

Three governing equations are necessary to solve for the pressure inside the fibrous preform as the three unknowns of this problem are the fluid pressure, velocity and density. In the case of viscous flow [6], the equations are: (1) the fluid mass conservation (assuming the preform does not deform while the fluid moves inside), (2) the momentum equation (Darcy's law) and (3) equation of state of an ideal gas. They result in equation (4) that is implemented in the numerical model solved for the pressure.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho v) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$v = \frac{\bar{K}}{\phi \mu} \cdot \nabla P \quad (2)$$

Where ρ and μ are the fluid density and viscosity, respectively, ϕ is the preform porosity and v is the pore-scale fluid velocity.

In the case of anisotropic porous media, the permeability \bar{K} is a symmetric third second order tensor:

$$\bar{K} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} & K_{xz} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} & K_{yz} \\ K_{zx} & K_{zy} & K_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$pV = nRT \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\bar{K}}{\phi \mu} \cdot P \nabla P \right) \quad (4)$$

In this study, the permeability tensor principal axes (1,2,3) are considered aligned with the experimental bench axes (x,y,z) so that the permeability tensor is simplified as a diagonal tensor such as:

$$\bar{\bar{K}} = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & K_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

To identify the permeability tensor by inverse method, two models (Fig. 7) are build according to the experimental configurations:

- **Step 1** (in-plane flow): a 2D model where the initial pressure condition reads the initial pressure P_0 applied to the 2D preform domain. As a Dirichlet boundary condition, the transient inlet pressure that is measured by the cavity sensor (P4) is applied around the 2D preform domain. The pressure P is then solved for K_1 and K_2 intervals to get pressure located in points P1, P2 and P3 used in identification of the in-plane permeability components K_1 and K_2 by the inverse method.
- **Step 2** (transverse flow): a 3D model where the initial pressure condition reads the initial pressure P_0 applied to the 3D preform domain. There is a no flow condition applied to the top and bottom faces of the domain. As Dirichlet boundary conditions, the centre point on the bottom face is set as the inlet and the cavity transient pressure (measured by P4) is applied to the four lateral faces. The in-plane permeability components K_1 and K_2 previously identified are set as model parameters and the pressure is solved for a K_3 interval. Pressure located in points P1, P2, P3 and P5 are saved to be used in identification of the transverse permeability component K_3 by the inverse method.

Both models are initialize with the preform dimensions, the material parameters such as the fluid (air) viscosity μ and the fibrous preform porosity ϕ .

Figure 7: Boundary conditions applied to the step 1 (left) and step 2 (left) numerical models

3.3 $\bar{\bar{K}}$ determination by inverse method

The full 3D permeability tensor of the fibrous preform $\bar{\bar{K}}$ is determined with an inverse method illustrated in the figure 8. First, the in-plane components K_1 and K_2 are identified by minimizing a cumulated error ϵ (equation (5)) by time step on each pressure sensor measurement and for each K_1 and K_2 couple, between experimental measurement P_{exp} (step 1) and the corresponding numerical solution P_{sim} (2D model of step 1).

$$\epsilon(K_1, K_2) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_t \left(\frac{P_{1_{exp}} - P_{1_{sim}}}{P_{1_{exp}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{P_{2_{exp}} - P_{2_{sim}}}{P_{2_{exp}}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{P_{3_{exp}} - P_{3_{sim}}}{P_{3_{exp}}} \right)^2} \quad (5)$$

The couple (K_1, K_2) is solution of the minimum cumulated error ϵ , such as shown in figure 9.

Figure 8: Schematic of the inverse method used to determine the 3D permeability tensor of an anisotropic 3D fibrous preform.

Secondly, the 3D numerical model for step 2 is solved with the identified in-plane permeability K_1 and K_2 as parameters for a set of K_3 values. Then, the transverse component K_3 is identified by minimizing the cumulated error (K_3) (Fig. 9), as in equation (6), between experimental measurement P_{exp} (step 2) and the corresponding numerical solution P_{sim} (3D model of step 2).

$$\epsilon(K_3) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_t} \sum_t \left(\frac{P_{1exp} - P_{1sim}}{P_{1exp}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{P_{2exp} - P_{2sim}}{P_{2exp}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{P_{3exp} - P_{3sim}}{P_{3exp}} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{P_{5exp} - P_{5sim}}{P_{5exp}} \right)^2} \quad (6)$$

Figure 9: Plots of the cumulated errors $\epsilon(K_1, K_2)$ for in-plane (left) and $\epsilon(K_3)$ for transverse (right) permeability tensor components identification.

5 CONCLUSIONS

To control particle-filled RTM in 3D fibrous preforms, a model should be built so as to couple flow in porous media, particle filtration, and material properties' evolution induced by the filtration phenomenon. Such a model requires material properties related to particle-filled resin rheology and fibrous preform permeability as inputs. To do so, a material characterization work was conducted, which consisted first in the study of particle-filled fluid rheology, also in the understanding of the 3D fibrous preform using micro-tomography and then in the preform permeability determination.

A new experimental methodology to measure a 3D anisotropic fibrous preform permeability tensor using a transient air flow has been described. This fast and non-destructive method is based on the gas pressure measurement at different locations of the preform during the transient air flow. By decoupling the measurements into two distinct steps, in-plane and transverse, the 3D permeability tensor components can be identified by an inverse method. To do so, a cumulated error by time steps and between the experimental pressure sensor measurements and numerical pressure solution is minimized. First, the in-plane permeability tensor components K_1 and K_2 are identified by solving a 2D numerical model. Then, a 3D numerical model, replicating the second step of the experiment, is solved with the identified K_1 and K_2 as inputs to determine the remaining transverse component K_3 .

The material data generated from the characterization will further be implemented in the coupled flow-filtration model. Perspectives are to assess and validate the model with experimental protocol.

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